

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP7 - Communication and Dissemination Report on Dissemination Activities

20.12.2023

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Report on Dissemination Activities (COESO D.7.5)

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Contents

I. Introduction	4
1. Report Summary	4
2. COESO project overview	4
a. COESO objectives	4
b. COESO activities	4
3. COESO results	5
a. 35 public project deliverables organized within seven different work packages	5
b. Individual blogs and project results from 10 COESO pilot projects	7
c. Scientific publications	9
II. Dissemination Overview	9
1. Dissemination management	10
2. Dissemination Plan	10
a. Target Audiences and Communication Channels	11
3. Dissemination measures and achievements	12
a. Dissemination measures applied to all results	12
b. Dissemination measures for specific results	13
1. Open Call	13
2. Pilot blogs and pilot outputs	14
3. VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation)	17
4. Funding Advocacy	24
5. Cooperation Analytics	27
6. Mutual Learning	28
7. Communication about SSH Citizen Science	29
III. Assessment of Dissemination Measures	32
1. Key Performance Indicators	32
a. Communication KPIs	33
b. Relevant Project KPIs	33
IV. Conclusion	34
Annexes	36
Annex 1: Dissemination Summary Table	36
Annex 2: COESO pilot communication activities and outputs	37

I. Introduction

1. Report Summary

This “[Report on Dissemination Activities](#) (COESO D.7.5)” describes and highlights the achievements of the communication and dissemination activities that took place during the COESO project implementation. In section 1, the COESO project overall objectives and aims are briefly recollectored, and the key project results for dissemination are listed. Section 2 summarizes the dissemination management structure, methods, plans, and achievements. In the final section, the relevant project Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are reviewed with a corresponding discussion about their relation to the dissemination achievements.

2. COESO project overview

a. COESO objectives

The [COESO project](#) (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues) is a 3-year participatory research project, funded by the European Commission through a “Science with and for Society” grant, and supported by the [OPERAS research infrastructure](#). The COESO project fosters the development of citizen science and participatory research in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) by engaging with and bridging the European social science and humanities community, the citizen science community, and the open scholarly communication community. As part of this bridging endeavor, COESO also collaborates with existing communities such as [Hypotheses.org](#) and [EU-Citizen.Science](#). Moreover, it explores the frontiers of public engagement innovation in social sciences and humanities disciplines through mutual learning exercises among COESO project and pilot project members, as well as through the experimentation with different formats of presenting project results for and with diverse stakeholders. A number of outputs are generated through COESO, but **the most significant output is the development of VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation), a virtual hub that supports social sciences and humanities researchers and society members** to find each other and get access to appropriate tools and resources to co-create research projects for collaborative knowledge production and sharing.

COESO project objectives:

1. Support collaborative practices
2. Enhance financial support
3. Leverage transmedia in public engagement
4. Engage with stakeholders from different backgrounds
5. Identify obstacles and assess efficient collaborations
6. Experiment with new methodologies

b. COESO activities

The COESO project addresses the challenges that hinder the development of citizen science in the social sciences and humanities through a bundle of interrelated and coordinated activities:

- Provide funding and a supportive environment to 10 citizen science pilot projects

reflecting a variety of citizen science practices and challenges in the social sciences and humanities (objective 1, objective 4, objective 6)

- Produce knowledge on citizen science co-creation practices in the social sciences and humanities through mutual learning exercises with the pilot projects and through the exploration of transmedia and/or multimodal public engagement practices (objective 1, objective 3, objective 4, objective 6)
- Respond to the SSH citizen science needs through the development of a dedicated online hub – [VERA](#) (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation) (objective 1, objective 4)
- Raise awareness of specific SSH citizen science funding needs among the European research funders and SSH research community (objective 1, objective 2)
- Experiment with developing a “Cooperation Analytics” tool for measuring and self-assessing the quality of collaboration within participatory research projects (objective 5)

3. COESO results

Below is a comprehensive list of the COESO project results – that is, any public document, data, tool, etc. that was created through the project activities. Included in brackets, after each result title, are corresponding dissemination statistics. Detailed descriptions of each result can be found under the respective links provided for the reader to directly access more information about the result.

a. 35 public project deliverables organized within seven different work packages

Work Package 1 - Project Coordination and Management

[Data Management Plan](#) (COESO D.1.2) published July 2021, update June 2022, update December 2023 [54 views; 48 downloads¹]

[Policy Brief 1 - Fostering funding for citizen science in the social sciences and humanities](#) (COESO D.1.4), published June 2022 [1K views; 483 downloads]

[COESO Policy Brief #2](#) (COESO D.1.5), published December 2023

Work Package 2 - Pilot Implementation and Open Call

[Open Call Guide for Applicants](#) (COESO D.2.1), published May 2022 [11 views; 6 downloads]

[COESO pilots' blogs on the Hypotheses.org academic platform](#) (COESO D.2.2) [Pilots 1-10 as listed in next section], published Dec 2021 [139 views; 109 downloads]

Also nine deliverables within WP2 were created within the first five pilot projects; they are

¹ Unless otherwise noted, the statistics reported in this document, such as number of views and downloads, were obtained on December 11 2023.

listed in the next section under the specific pilot they relate to. The first five pilot projects were “built-into” the COESO project and grant agreement, whereas the second five pilots were chosen through an Open Call process Nov 2021-May 2022. Therefore only the first five projects had specific planned deliverables.

Work Package 3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA)

[Data Management Plan](#) (COESO D.1.2) published July 2021, update June 2022, update December 2023 [54 views; 48 downloads]

[Policy Brief 1 - Fostering funding for citizen science in the social sciences and humanities](#) (COESO D.1.4), published June 2022 [1K views; 483 downloads]

[COESO Policy Brief #2](#) (COESO D.1.5), published December 2023 [no available statistics at time of writing]

Work Package 4 - Funding Citizen Science

[Landscape study on Citizen Science funding](#) (COESO D.4.1), published July 2021 [806 views; 548 downloads]

[Funding tool integration](#) (COESO D.4.2), published January 2023 [36 views; 33 downloads]

[Funding Advocacy Action Plan](#) (COESO D.4.3), published October 2021 [916 views; 324 downloads]

Work Package 5 - Cooperation Quality Assessment

[Cooperation analytics: criteria grid and development \(COESO D.5.1\)](#), published September 2021 [279 views; 195 downloads]

[Report on Test and Final Development of the Cooperation Analytics](#) (COESO D.5.2), published June 2022, [91 views; 68 downloads]

[Report on activism and science within Citizen Science](#) (COESO D.5.3) published December 2023 [no statistics available at time of writing]

Work Package 6 - Enhancing Public Engagement in Citizen Science through Transmedia Writing and Mutual Learning

[Public Engagement, Mutual Learning, and Multimodal Practices in Citizen Science: report on the activities of WP6](#) (COESO D.6.1), published September 2023 [77 views; 36 downloads]

[São José, a transmedia and multimodal website on the Lisbon Tourism Observatory engagement in the urban space](#) (COESO D.6.2), published December 2021 [135 views; 75 downloads]

Work Package 7 - Communication and Dissemination

[Communication and Dissemination Strategy](#) (COESO D.7.1), published April 2021 [200 views; 175 downloads]

[Dissemination Material Guide](#) (COESO D.7.2), published April 2021 [98 views; 80 downloads]

[Podcast series: “Exploring Citizen Science”](#) (COESO D.7.3), published between January 2023 and July 2023, [1,798 downloads]

[Article series: “Common Grounds”](#) (COESO D.7.4), published between Apr 2023 and Dec 2023) [2,150 clicks, cumulative – including all language versions of all articles]

[Report on Dissemination Activities](#) (COESO D.7.5), published December 2023 [no available statistics at time of writing]

[Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science](#) (COESO D.7.6), published December 2023 [no available statistics at time of writing]

b. Individual blogs and project results from 10 COESO pilot projects

Each COESO pilot project was required to create an academic blog on Hypotheses.org, where all members of the project (academic and non-academic) could contribute their insights to showcase their research. This was important to the COESO project in that it helped to give visibility to citizen science practices within the social sciences and humanities disciplines. In addition to their blogs, the first 5 pilot projects also published reports at the end of their projects. The second 5 pilot projects each submitted a final report (not public) to COESO, and pilot #7 (AGORage) also produced a toolkit in multiple languages as a result of their research. All the pilots’ results are listed below. The pilot blogs and the community management to support them are elaborated in detail with the report, [COESO pilots’ blogs on the Hypotheses.org academic platform](#) (COESO D.2.2), which is listed above. For a full list of each of the pilots’ communication and dissemination activities, see annex 2.

Pilot #1 - Mass tourism’s impact on urban communities

Blog: <https://civtur.hypotheses.org/>, opened Oct 2021 [ave. monthly visitors: 70]

[Lisbon Tourism Observatory Final Report](#) (COESO D.2.3) published Jan 2023 [124 views; 115 downloads]

Pilot #2 - Dancing Philosophy: Desire through dance and philosophy

Blog: <https://dansophie.hypotheses.org/>, opened October 2021, [ave. monthly visitors: 77]

[Documenting collaborations with video annotation: MemoRekall Capsules](#) (COESO D.2.4) [pilot 2], published May 2022 [176 views; 73 downloads]

[Dancing Philosophy – Choreographic Score](#) (COESO D.2.5), published June 2022 [280 views; 152 downloads]

[The movement of an embodied thought: Pilot 2 Dancing Philosophy Report](#) (COESO D.2.6) [pilot 2], published June 2022 [272 views; 131 downloads]

Pilot #3 - Social impacts of redistributing property confiscated from the mafia

Blog: <https://usbc.hypotheses.org/>, opened November 2021 [ave. monthly visitors: 61]

[Solutions journalism outputs](#) (COESO D.2.7) [pilot 3], published June 2022 [101 views; 61 downloads]

Pilot #4 - Tools and databases to increase the impact of investigative journalism

Blog: <https://thebackstory.hypotheses.org/>, opened November 2021 [ave. monthly visitors: 11]

[Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases](#) (COESO D.2.8) [pilot 4], published April 2022 [197 views; 86 downloads]

[Report on the technical and legal framework for sharing confidential data](#) (COESO D.2.9) [pilot 4], published March 2022 [219 views; 87 downloads]

Pilot #5 - Growing migrant knowledge: Contemporary and historical perspectives

Blog: <https://migconn.hypotheses.org/> opened November 2021 [ave. monthly visitors: 26]

[“Writing Across Borders” outputs](#) (COESO D.2.10) [pilot 5], published December 2022 [47 views; 43 downloads]

Pilot #6 - Digital Mapping with Disabled Citizens (DiMDiCi)

Blog: <https://dimdici.hypotheses.org/> opened November 2022 [ave. monthly visitors: 38]

Pilot #7 - Ageing in a Caring Community (AGORAge)

Blog: <https://agorage.hypotheses.org/> opened November 2022 [ave. monthly visitors: 46]

AGORAge Caring Community Toolkit - [English](#), [Italian](#), [French](#), [Catalan](#), [Spanish](#) [606 views; 505 downloads, cumulative, including all language versions]

Pilot #8 - Women Water Watch (wWw)

Blog: <https://waterwatch.hypotheses.org/> opened October 2022 [ave. monthly visitors: 33]

Pilot #9 - Playful Futures

Blog: <https://playfutures.hypotheses.org/> opened October 2022 [ave. monthly visitors: 22]

Pilot #10 - LUNCH-BOX-MONITOR

Blog: <https://lunchbox.hypotheses.org/> opened November 2022 [ave. monthly visitors: 18]

c. Scientific publications

The following scientific articles, related to the COESO project, have been reported to us by the consortium and pilot members. At least two other publications are in the process of being written.

- Riccò I., De Stefani A. & Anleu Hernández C. (2022) Notes de Recerca: AGORAge. Arxiu d'Etnografia de Catalunya (24), pp.238-242. DOI: [10.17345/aec24.232-241](https://doi.org/10.17345/aec24.232-241)
 - Research notes based on work completed in Pilot #7, Ageing in a Caring Community (AGORAge)
- Smaniotto, A., & Passani, A. (2023). Citizen Science with and within the Social Sciences and the Humanities. Guest editors' preface *Etica & Politica / Ethics & Politics*. <https://www.openstarts.units.it/handle/10077/35349>
 - Preface referencing COESO and its underlying principles
- Smaniotto, A., & Jonathan Chibois (2023) Open digital infrastructures for bridging professional cultures: the case of extreme science between journalism and research. *Open Research Europe*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 16, 2023 <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/3-3/v1>
 - Article includes section discussing insights from COESO project to discuss how dedicated infrastructures support communities of practice
- Smaniotto, A., & Passani, A. (Eds.) (2023) *Etica & Politica / Ethics & Politics* (2023) XXV/2. (n.d.). Retrieved December 16, 2023 <https://www.openstarts.units.it/collections/67ad1544-5716-4b37-85ac-5d140092d724>
 - Journal edition dedicated to citizen science in the social sciences and humanities for which the preface (referenced above) was written

II. Dissemination Overview

This second part elaborates on all aspects of the COESO dissemination activities, beginning with an overview of how they were managed, planned, and executed, and then covering, by topic, the specific dissemination measures taken for particular results, and their corresponding achievements. According to a brochure by the European Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Helpdesk, “dissemination” refers to the transfer of “knowledge and results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research”.² We would add that transferring knowledge is not only a technical transaction of making the information accessible and findable; it also requires taking proactive measures to creatively

² The European IPR Helpdesk (2018). Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>, p. 13.

present the relevance of the information to the pertinent communities in an engaging and attractive manner. Therefore, within the COESO project, special attention was given to, not only on deciding when and where the results were made available, but presenting them in an engaging manner, often through blog posts and social media, designed to encourage and inspire the relevant community members to utilize the results for their own work. Additionally, two specific communication actions using mainstream media formats – podcasts and online magazine articles – were built into the project, specifically to be more appealing and expand our audience and the uptake of the results.

1. Dissemination management

The dissemination activities were directed by work package 7 (WP7), which involved eight consortium member organizations – including four research organizations (EHESS, MWS, CRIA, Sciences Po), one small tech company (Net7), a non-profit foundation dedicated to promoting citizen science (Ibercivis), and two news media agencies (Bulle Media and Babel International) – based in six different countries (France, Germany Italy, Portugal, Spain, Belgium). Thus, COESO's dissemination actions were a coordinated, international, and interdisciplinary effort that leveraged the connections and available resources of the entire project team.

Members of WP7 kept abreast of issues and concerns within the European citizen science community, which is vibrant and active throughout the continent and united through actions coordinated mostly through ECSA (European Citizen Science Association), the Living Knowledge International science shop network, and the different national citizen science associations. The project coordinator, for example, attended the monthly ECSA Networking Working Group and bimonthly RRI (Responsible Research and Innovation) ecosystem meetings; another member from Net7 attended the Cross-SwafS (Science with and for Society) forum for responsible open science every two months; and other members attended regular meetings for additional citizen science projects, of which their organizations were also consortium members. COESO consortium member involvement in all of these cross-project meetings ensured that the project team stayed engaged with the relevant communities and was always up-to-date about the relevant channels for dissemination of COESO results.

At monthly WP7 meetings, the consortium members discussed the project's activities and needs, in terms of communication and dissemination actions, exchanged information about events and activities happening in the pertinent national, international and professional communities, made joint decisions about who would attend which relevant upcoming events, and brainstormed on the most effective formats and channels for project results to be spread to the target audiences. In between these meetings, the WP7 leader and the project coordinator conducted weekly check-ins to ensure constant alignment on all project activities.

2. Dissemination Plan

Three months into the COESO project, in March 2021, WP7 created an ambitious and comprehensive [Communication and Dissemination Strategy](#) (COESO D7.1). This document laid out, in detail, the target audiences and corresponding planned dissemination measures for the entire three-year project, ensuring that every target audience would be amply served with the various types of project outputs and by the chosen communication channels. During the ensuing project implementation, the plan served as a guide that was often followed closely, and sometimes altered to meet the specific needs of the dynamic project at hand. At the forefront of every

decision was the priority to adhere to the overall project aims and goals, taking into account the resources available. Any deviations from the plan were made consciously and with solid reasoning.

a. Target Audiences and Communication Channels

COESO’s target audiences and communication channels and the logic behind identifying them are described in detail starting on page 8 of the [Communication and Dissemination Strategy](#) (COESO D.7.1). Below, they are briefly recalled to provide the necessary context for describing the dissemination actions in the following section.

COESO has 4 target audiences, here listed in order from the highest to the lowest level of focus:

1. SSH researchers and societal actors who are already involved in citizen science. That is, individuals who are already incorporating citizen science practices into their work.
2. Research funding organizations and European policy makers of all levels.
3. SSH researchers and societal actors who are not yet involved in citizen science activities.
4. Researchers from other disciplines, research organizations and universities at large, and service providers, such as libraries and research infrastructures.

The following channels were designated for dissemination activities for the CEOSO project results. As the [Communication and Dissemination Strategy](#) (COESO D.7.1) explains in detail, COESO’s results will be sustained, after the project is over, by the [OPERAS](#) research infrastructure, and therefore the well established [OPERAS](#) communication channels were already used for communication and dissemination purposes during the COESO project.

1. Zenodo [OPERAS](#) community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu>
2. COESO project website with incorporated blogging space: <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/>
3. COESO X/Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/COESOEU>
4. [OPERAS](#) research infrastructure social media accounts
 - a. <https://twitter.com/OPERASEU>
 - b. <https://www.linkedin.com/company/operas/>
 - c. <https://www.instagram.com/operaseu>
5. Recurring newsletter contributions:

Newsletter	COESO contributions date range	# of COESO contributions	# Subscribers
OPERAS Newsletter (quarterly) (archives)	Jan 2021-Dec 2023	10	473 (on Nov 30 2023)
The Citizen Engagement Quarterly (quarterly joint newsletter for five Horizon 2020 projects - MOSAIC, SocketTs, IRIS Smart Cities, COESO and FRANCIS)	Nov 2021 - July 2023	6	178 (on Nov 29 2023)

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) newsletter (monthly)	March 2021 - Dec 2023	6	2,334 (on Nov 30 2023)
Citizen Science Lighthouse: ECS Collaboration group newsletter (monthly)	June 2023-Nov 2023	4	1275 (on Nov 30 2023)

6. Distribution of materials and oral informational presentations at events, meetings, conferences
7. Project’s final conference: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) in Paris Oct 19-21 2023 [170 participants/ 218 registered]

3. Dissemination measures and achievements

In this section, the specific actions taken to disseminate the COESO results are described, beginning with a summary of actions that were applied to all results, and then elaborating on additional actions taken for particular results.

a. Dissemination measures applied to all results

Each of the public COESO deliverable documents was uploaded onto Zenodo, within the [OPERAS](#) Research Infrastructure community, in open access format with a CC BY 4.0 license and tagged with “COESO Project” along with other relevant tags, depending on the topic of the deliverable. A “[Resources](#)” page on the COESO website lists every COESO deliverable followed by a short description and a link to download it from Zenodo. The following mainly administrative-focused deliverables of the project were published on Zenodo to make the processes within the project visible and openly accessible for everyone:

- [Data Management Plan](#) (COESO D.1.2) published July 2021, update June 2022, update December 2023 [54 views; 48 downloads]
- [Communication and Dissemination Strategy](#) (COESO D.7.1), published April 2021 [200 views; 175 downloads]
- [Dissemination Material Guide](#) (COESO D.7.2), published April 2021 [98 views; 80 downloads]
- [Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results](#) (PEDR) (COESO D.7.7), published July 2021, update December 2023 [138 views; 96 downloads – as of Dec 11, 2023]
- [Funding tool integration](#) (COESO D.4.2), published January 2023 [36 views; 33 downloads]
- [COESO pilots’ blogs on the Hypotheses.org academic platform](#) (COESO D.2.2) [Pilots 1-10 as listed in next section], published Dec 2021 [139 views; 109 downloads]

Additionally, the COESO project as a whole, including all the results, was disseminated through its final conference, [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) in Paris, October 19-21, 2023. For maximum visibility and to attract a variety of audiences, the conference was coordinated together with the PRO-Ethics project. The event included **3 keynotes, 27 breakout sessions, 2 plenary panels, 16 posters and networking activities, bringing together 170 participants** (218 people registered) from a variety of professional interests and backgrounds. With a focus on citizen science in the social sciences and humanities, as well as on integrating participatory approaches at the research

funding stage, the conference served as a networking opportunity for citizen science practitioners, policy makers, funders, research service providers and more. The conference was heavily promoted – before, during and after the event – through both consortiums’ communication channels with photos, videos, posters, social media posts, blog posts, emails, flyers, and newsletter announcements. The COESO results were presented in different formats within the conference, and those details will be described in the respective sections of this report.

b. Dissemination measures for specific results

For deliverables other than those listed in the preceding section, additional actions, including social media posts and blog posts on the COESO website that include links to the corresponding Zenodo-doi, were used to bring attention to the document and highlight or expand upon the main points. Some results in particular were given even more attention through the creation of printed informational materials, such as posters at conferences and the creation and distribution of postcards and stickers. The additional dissemination actions for each of these outputs are described in detail below. They are grouped by topic.

1. Open Call

Achievements:

Wide dissemination of the Open Call for applications to be one of the five new COESO pilot projects (up to 50,000 Euros per project), utilizing **multilingual** and **multi-modal** strategies, and taking advantage of the **diverse** COESO consortium member **networks**, attracted **172 applications from 15 countries**. The Open Call guide and dissemination strategy may be useful for future projects implementing a cascade funding framework.

[Open Call Guide for Applicants](#) (COESO D.2.1) (note: during the application process, the open call guide was linked to a file directly on the COESO website; this is why the Zenodo version received few views/downloads - 11 views; 6 downloads – as of Dec 11, 2023)

COESO’s Open Call, for which 172 applications were received, opened on November 30, 2021 and

closed on March 31, 2022. The number of applications exceeded the expectations of the COESO consortium team and therefore we consider the Open Call process itself to be successful and important to share, as a resource for future projects with a “cascade funding” framework. Thus, the Open Call is featured at the top of the COESO website “[Resources](#)” page. From there, the text describing the Open Call and the entire process, the slide deck corresponding to a live Open Call info webinar that was conducted, and a document of answers to Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) can all be accessed. The “Open Call Guide for Applicants” as well as the “Final Public Report” are also publicly available on Zenodo. To distribute information about the open call, while it was happening, a blog post, “[Apply now to be one of COESO’s 5 new pilots projects!](#)” was written and promoted, informational emails (in various languages) were distributed through COESO consortium networks, and a social media campaign was employed. A follow-up blog post, “[COESO’s Open Call: How to select just five](#)” and follow-up posts on social media were also published.

2. Pilot blogs and pilot outputs

Achievements:

10 research blogs, created by the 10 COESO pilot projects, were given visibility through combinations of: 37 blog posts on the COESO website, numerous social media posts, 2 academic conference posters, 5 mainstream online magazine articles, 9 podcasts episodes, newsletter contributions and printed postcards. All together, the blogs were **visited 8,345 times over a 26 month period**. On average, each blog was visited 40 times per month. **Nine project reports** and **one toolkit**, produced by the individual pilots, were disseminated through Zenodo links on the COESO website, and promoted through conference presentations, blogging, social media, and newsletter contributions. Cumulatively, they have been **viewed 2,292 times and downloaded 1,403 times**.

Each of the 10 COESO pilot projects was required and supported to create and maintain an academic blog on Hypotheses.org to document and give visibility to their research processes. The reasoning and administrative details for this process are described in detail in [COESO pilots’ blogs on the Hypotheses.org academic platform](#) (COESO D.2.2). In addition to supporting the blogging process, COESO utilized the pilot blogs as examples of research practices (both blogging practices and the methodologies used within the pilots’ research) that engage communities. To highlight the practices, the WP7 team published [blog posts on the COESO website](#) throughout the project to share about the pilots’ research methodologies and outputs and link readers to the corresponding pilots’ blogs. In total, COESO published 37 of these pilot-focused blog posts, including blogs that are written in languages other than English, as some of the pilots were operating their projects in other languages. Each blog post was promoted through social media posts, directly tagging the research team member and/or the organization where they work.

1. [Cafébabel Terrains Communs: “Bridging the Gap: A Deep Dive into Collaborative Narratives”](#)
2. [Poster gallery of COESO pilots](#)
3. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #9. Online collaboration for an international Role Play game](#)
4. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #8. Women water warriors](#)
5. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #10. The co-created journey into the children’s lunchboxes](#)
6. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #7. A caring community in progress](#)
7. [AGORAge Caring community toolkit. Recommendations for any person or group wishing to create a caring community](#)
8. [Dietro le quinte del Pilot #7 AGORAge: una comunità in costruzione](#)

9. [How can philosophy be danced? Lessons learned from Pilot #2 Dancing Philosophy](#)
10. [Exploring the Impacts of Mass Tourism: A Community-Centric Approach in Lisbon's Santo António Parish](#)
11. [A look back at the Babel Academy. Journalists and researchers discussed the social reuse of confiscated assets.](#)
12. [Growing migrant knowledge: Pilot #5 Contemporary and historical perspectives](#)
13. [Empowering Inclusivity & Diversity in Citizen Science: Pilot #6 Digital Mapping with Disabled Citizens \(DiMDiCi\)](#)
14. [Insight into the nutritional quality of school lunch-boxes: introduction of the pilot #10 Lunch-Box monitor project](#)
15. [Mapping the water quality from the river to the glass in Tanzania: presentation of the pilot #8 Women Water Watch project](#)
16. [São José: a multimodal citizen science project exploring tourism in Lisbon](#)
17. [An online Role Play Game to address the sea level rising issue: introduction of the pilot #9 Playful Futures project](#)
18. [Ageing in a Caring Community: presentation of the pilot #7 AGORAge project](#)
19. [Engagement with Lisbon citizens through COESO's pilot #1](#)
20. [How to start an investigation on sensitive data without taking personal risks](#)
21. [The Babel Academy, journalists and researchers investigate the social uses of confiscated assets](#)
22. [La Babel Academy, des journalistes et chercheur·euses enquêtent sur l'usage social des biens confisqués](#)
23. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #5. Growing migrant knowledge: Contemporary and historical perspectives](#)
24. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #1. Local partners collaborate together to study the impacts of tourism in Lisbon](#)
25. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #3. A journalist-researcher duo meets those who are involved in citizen experimentation](#)
26. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #4 "Tools and databases to increase the impact of investigative journalism"](#)
27. [Behind the scenes: Pilot #2 "We can give each other the gift of the unknown"](#)
28. [Dans les coulisses du pilote #3 : Un duo journaliste-chercheur à la rencontre de celles et ceux qui font de l'expérimentation citoyenne](#)
29. [Dans les coulisses du pilote #2 "Nous faire le cadeau de l'inconnu"](#)
30. [Apprendre de l'expérience de l'usage social de biens confisquées en Italie, à travers le journalisme de solution et l'étude socio-politique](#)
31. [Dansophie: sur scène avec son public](#)
32. [Mass tourism's impact on everyday life in Lisbon](#)
33. [Expanding Migrant Knowledge: Contemporary and historical perspectives](#)
34. [Dancing Philosophy: desire, recognition, body, language](#)
35. [Datasets for two: strengthening the impact of investigative journalism in collaboration with academic research](#)
36. [Dansophie: désir, reconnaissance, corps, parole](#)
37. [Dataset per due: rafforzare l'impatto del giornalismo investigativo in collaborazione con la ricerca accademica](#)

In many cases, the blog posts, written based on the pilots' final reports to COESO, highlighted their outputs: [Lisbon Tourism Observatory Final Report](#) (COESO D.2.3), [Documenting collaborations with video annotation: MemoRekall Capsules](#) (COESO D.2.4), [Dancing Philosophy –](#)

[Choreographic Score](#) (COESO D.2.5), [The movement of an embodied thought: Pilot 2 Dancing Philosophy Report](#) (COESO D.2.6), [Solutions journalism outputs](#) (COESO D.2.7), [Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases](#) (COESO D.2.8), [Report on the technical and legal framework for sharing confidential data](#) (COESO D.2.9), and [“Writing Across Borders” outputs](#) (COESO D2.10) and the [AGORAge Caring Community Toolkit](#). In addition to the attention that COESO gave to the pilot results, the individual pilot members themselves presented at various conferences and meetings, including each presenting a poster and participating in various breakout sessions at [Connect.Collaborate.Create](#). (COESO’s final conference). We aimed to track the communication channels used and activities carried out by each pilot (see annex 2 for a comprehensive list), so that we could offer advice and support for increasing their projects’ visibility. The 10 COESO pilots address diverse specific societal issues: mass tourism, education and gender, resilient societies, fight against crime, societal change and migration, inclusivity in city planning, valorisation of ageing people in communities, accessing and using local knowledge and leadership for policy making/implementation, raising awareness on climate change, and food insecurities of children. Thus, they represented a diversity of disciplines and methodologies used in citizen science projects in the social sciences and humanities, and COESO’s WP7 team informed them of relevant conference opportunities and supported them with their applications whenever possible.

Additionally, as part of COESO’s goal to leverage transmedia in public engagement, pilot #1 (Mass Tourism’s impact on urban communities) experimented with a “transmedia website”, described in detail in [São José, a transmedia and multimodal website on the Lisbon Tourism Observatory engagement in the urban space](#) (COESO D.6.2) as well as in a blog post on Centre Norbert Elias website, [São José website : une analyse collective de l’expérience touristique à Lisbonne \(projet COESO\)](#). Because of its innovative nature, special attention was given to disseminating it and getting feedback on it, through participation in 15 academic conferences (estimated audience 750). This list of conferences can be found on page 65 of [Public Engagement, Mutual Learning, and Multimodal Practices in Citizen Science: report on the activities of WP6](#) (COESO D.6.1.). An exhibition presenting the website was also set up at [Connect.Collaborate.Create](#). (COESO’s final conference), with QR codes directing visitors to the website, and a specific session, *Session 1.1F: Participatory research storytelling and transmedia journeys*, was dedicated to the topic.

Additionally, the COESO pilot community manager co-created postcards with each pilot to feature their work through an engaging photo and a QR code to their blog. Printed and digital versions of the postcards were provided to the pilot members for them to distribute to their respective networks and communities; they were also handed out to participants at COESO’s final conference (Connect.Collaborate.Create.). The postcards include a QR code linking to VERA.

(Example of a pilot postcard - pilot 6; 1 postcard was created for each of the 10 pilots)

Moreover, each of the pilot project blogs and outputs are listed on the dedicated [pilots page](#) on the COESO website. The project as a whole, including the website, was given visibility through every communication action taken, including participation in the [Liber Conference](#) in June 2021, the [Open Access Tage conference](#) in September 2021, the [Citizen Social Science school](#) (CoAct) in September 2021, the presentation of a video on the first five pilots at the “Future of Citizen Science” conference, an online presentation at the C*Sci2022 conference in May 2022, and a series of online magazine articles and a series of podcasts (described in detail below), which highlighted different aspects of the pilot projects.

3. VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation)

Achievements:
 Once VERA went live in January 2023, it was **presented formally to the community 12 times**, (plus one webinar planned in January 2024) through in-person and online events. Additionally, five blog posts, weekly social media posts, a widget on Hypotheses.org, 10 newsletter contributions, a dedicated page on the COESO website, and close coordination with the [OPERAS](#) community supported the initial onboarding process. As of December 13, 2023 VERA has **174 person profiles** (70 of which are public; 40 self-identify as “academic”) and **82 project profiles** (15 of which are public), and in the last quarter of the COESO project, VERA has had **470 unique visitors** and **3030 homepage views**.

The website for the [VERA](#) hub is one of the COESO project’s key outputs. It is designed to support the SSH citizen science community, beyond the COESO project’s lifetime, and therefore significant effort was given to disseminate it to the community. VERA’s future, including its further development and community engagement and support activities around it, will be taken over by the [OPERAS](#) research infrastructure after the COESO project ends, which is why close coordination with the [OPERAS](#) communication team was essential to any dissemination work.

VERA’s development began with the start of the COESO project in January 2021, involving a netnography as described in this blogpost, [“First contact with citizen science communities”](#) (Nov 11 2021), which was accompanied by social media posts. In the first year, members of the COESO consortium began to collaborate with [OPERAS](#) by having relevant members attend the [OPERAS](#) “national node” meetings in Greece, Germany and France to present VERA as an upcoming

[OPERAS](#) “service for society” and to gather information about national funding schemes (more on funding activities in the following section). COESO published a blog post, [“COESO und die deutsche Community: Einblick in Citizen-Science-Projektförderung”](#) (June 8, 2021), and its translation, [“COESO and the German community: An insight into citizen science project funding”](#) (August 8, 2021), about the OPERAS-GER (Germany) meeting.

In January 2023, the beta version of the website was made live for the public. The co-creation process of the website and the technical components of the website are results that can be reused by others in their work, and the deliverables, [User Experience/User Interface design](#) (COESO D.3.1), published April 2022 and [VERA Core Design and Development](#) (COESO D.3.2), published December 2021, documenting these aspects were published and promoted via social media posts. Half way through the project, before the platform was finished, a blog post, [VERA \(Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation\)](#) (Aug 19 2022), shared with the community about the overall concept. And then, with the public release of VERA, a report, [Development of the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation \(VERA\) VERA Dashboard](#) (COESO D.3.3), published December 2022 informing about the dashboard was also written. Shortly afterwards, another technical report, [Matching Interface design \(for VERA\)](#) (COESO D.3.4), published March 2023, about the interface design was published. Finally, in June 2023, the last technical report, [Collaboration tools and services integration](#) (COESO D3.5), published June 2023, describing the tools featured within VERA was made public and accompanied by a blog post, [VERA - Using technology to bridge the gap between researchers and the public](#) (published Sept 14 2023). Each time a deliverable was published, corresponding social media posts promoted the reports to the community.

VERA website and trainings:

In order for the VERA website to be attractive to potential users, it should feature an ample number of person and project profiles. Therefore, once the website was live in January 2023, efforts were made to encourage the European citizen science and Open Science communities to join the VERA community. The COESO pilot projects were each required to add their project to VERA, to test it out for usability, and to provide feedback. As mentioned above, the pilot members were also provided with printed postcards that included their own project information as well as VERA information. Additional-VERA-specific postcards were designed, printed, and distributed to COESO pilot members and consortium members to distribute externally when attending meetings, conferences, engaging with clients, etc.

A tool for collaborative research with and for society

Discover
partners

Manage
projects

Find
funding

Get
visibility

**Virtual
Ecosystem for
Research
Activation**

Discover VERA, the online hub for activating Participatory Research within the **social sciences and humanities**.

Create profiles, find collaborators, manage projects, search for funding.

vera.operas-eu.org

VERA is developed within the COESO project for the OPERAS research infrastructure

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006325.

(VERA postcard, printed and distributed to COESO pilot and consortium members)

Besides engaging the COESO community to sign on to VERA and to help distribute information about it through printed and virtual-based media, COESO consortium members conducted VERA trainings and attended conferences to present VERA, in various contexts and formats, to the community. For example:

- **9th Living Knowledge Conference**, June 29, 2022 (Groningen): Alessia Smaniotto (EHESS/Open Edition) and Kelly Achenbach (Max Weber Foundation) engaged with participants through a poster presentation about the VERA co-design journey.
- **TRIPLE final conference**, February 1, 2023 (Bonn): Tiziana Lombardo (Net7) presented about how and why VERA was created and how to use VERA to support participatory research. (90 in-person and 31 online attendees))
- Cross SwafS meeting, April 6, 2023 (online): Tiziana Lombardo (Net7) presented VERA twice during the Cross-SwafS Stakeholder Forum for Responsible Open Science sessions, a bimonthly meeting, facilitated through the [ROSiE project](#) between September 2021 and June 2023, bringing together SwafS (a Horizon 2020 programme aiming at building effective cooperation between science and society) project members to share knowledge: in February 2022 a general overview of COESO, including the VERA design approach was given, and a VERA

demo was given on April 6, 2023.

- **OPERAS-GER Open Chat**, April 20 2023 (online): Tizana Lombardo (Net7) and Kelly Achenbach (Max Weber Foundation) gave a VERA demonstration and overview of the COESO project. (16 attendees, 30 registered participants)
- [LIBER Citizen Science Working Group](#), June 21, 2023: (online) Luca De Santis (Net7) and Kelly Achenbach (Max Weber Foundation) gave a VERA demonstration and overview of the COESO project. (14 attendees)
- [Impactful Citizen Science in the social sciences and humanities – a hands-on workshop exploring Participatory Research practices and a new tool to support them](#), June 30, 2023: (Bonn) Tiziana Lobardo (Net7), Alessia Smaniotto (EHESS/Open Edition), and Bill Costello (Net7) conducted a comprehensive, In-person training to the German community, organized by OPERAS-GER, to test a prototype for future trainings on using VERA to support participatory research in the social sciences and humanities (9 Participants).
- [Open Science Festival](#), August 31, 2023 (Rotterdam): Kelly Achenbach (Max Weber Foundation) provided information about VERA at a stand in the marketplace throughout the event. (photo credit: Pim Rusch)
- [Open Science Fair](#), September 21, 2023 (Madrid): Tiziana Lombardo (Net 7) gave a VERA demonstration.

- **Connect.Collaborate.Create. conference**, October 20, 2023 (Paris):
Marlen Töpfer (Max Weber Foundation) and Luca De Santis (Net 7) facilitated a VERA training session at the conference, *Session 1.1E: Supporting participatory research practices in the SSH with VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation)*, (13 participants in

session). Tiziana Lombardo (Net 7) and Sy Holsinger ([OPERAS](#)) presented VERA as part of the session “2.1G - Co-created solutions for citizen science platform.” Additionally, the QR code to VERA was posted on the wall of every session room and a VERA postcard was included in a bag given to every conference participant. (170 conference attendees)

(photo by Emilia Da Silva Rosario, Ereb Studio)

- [Falling Walls Science Summit](#), November 7, 2023 (Berlin): Kelly Achenbach (Max Weber Foundation) gave a 5 minute [pitch](#) about COESO, including VERA, to an audience of around 100 people. The COESO project was one of 20 winning projects, chosen from 207 applications across 70 countries, to participate in the Falling Walls Engage category.

- [Munin Conference](#), November 20, 2023 (Tromso) : Alessia Smaniotto (EHESS/ Open Edition) gave a 20 minute [presentation](#) (time stamp 1:22-1:46) about COESO, including VERA, to an in-presence audience of 80 people and 230 watching the live stream.

- [1° National Conference Citizen Science Italy](#), November 24, 2023 (Pisa): Tiziana Lombardo (Net7) and Luca De Santis (Net7) showcased VERA at a marketplace booth throughout the conference. (120 conference attendees)

- [Text+](#) IO-Lecture, November 30, 2024 (online): Marlen Töpfer (Max Weber Foundation) gave a presentation on VERA to members of Text+ community (10 participants). Afterwards, Text+ wrote a blog post, [“Text+ und Citizen Science?”](#) (published Dec 12, 2023).
- [ECSA webinar](#) (planned), January 16, 2024: Tiziana Lombardo (Net 7) will give an online VERA demo to the citizen science community. The event will be recorded and available on the ECSA website; the video will also be embedded into the COESO website.

Additionally, a page on the [COESO website](#) is dedicated to VERA; VERA is listed as a resource on the [Eu-citizen.science platform](#); and VERA is featured on the [OPERAS website](#) and is also listed in the [EOSC-Marketplace](#). The [VERA widget](#) (COESO D.3.6) appears on the dashboard of every Hypotheses account, ensuring that Hypotheses users are exposed to VERA's presence and updated on newly added projects. Hypotheses.org hosts over 35,000 users and over 7,000 blogs.

A blog post, [The VERA widget on Hypotheses](#), announcing the VERA widget was published on the COESO website in October 2023 and accompanied by a social media post.

[OPERAS national nodes](#) representatives in 10 countries (17 participants overall) have been specifically trained on the VERA hub and have been provided with materials, hosted on language/country specific landing pages on the VERA website, to conduct trainings and informational sessions in their respective countries during the first half of 2024. Also, contributions in the following newsletters directed readers to the VERA website throughout the last year of the project:

- March 2023: Citizen Engagement Quarterly
- November 2022: Citizen Engagement Quarterly
- July 2022: Citizen Engagement Quarterly
- March 2022: Citizen Engagement Quarterly
- June 2023: ECS Lighthouse
- February 2023 OPERAS
- June 2023 OPERAS

- September 2023 OPERAS
- May 2023 ECSA
- March 2023 ECSA

Furthermore, the [OPERAS](#) newsletter (quarterly) will continue to feature the VERA service in every future newsletter.

In September 2023, Mixpanel was integrated into VERA to track where people click on certain areas of the website; until that time, statistics on the number of visitors to VERA were unavailable. The Mixpanel statistics indicate that between September 2023 and December 11, 2023, there were 470 unique visitors on VERA and a total of 3030 homepage views.

4. Funding Advocacy

Achievements:

By making connections through workshops and then following up through blog posts, social media campaigns, and presentations at conferences, COESO's funding advocacy activities not only directly engaged with representatives from **35 different funding entities**, but also the related reports have received significant attention: COESO's **Landscape study** on citizen science has been **viewed 806 times and downloaded 548 times**; COESO's **funding policy brief** has been **viewed 916 times and downloaded 324 times** (numbers as of Dec 11, 2023).

COESO's funding advocacy activities aimed to raise awareness of specific SSH citizen science funding needs among European research funders and the social science and humanities research community. The advocacy activities began with conducting research and publishing a study, [Landscape study on Citizen Science funding](#) (COESO D.4.1) on July 23, 2021, about what funding already exists, thus creating a baseline of knowledge to inform the future actions that COESO would develop. Afterwards, the study results were described through a blog post, "[Landscape study on citizen science funding schemes for social sciences and the humanities](#)" (July 29, 2021) on the COESO website, and further input was requested from funders through another blogpost: "[WANTED: funders of social science and humanities research using citizen science methodologies](#)" (August 5, 2021). These were duplicated on the [Ibercivis website](#), and linked to through social media posts.

Following the research work, Alicia Moreno Muñoz (Ibercivis) presented a poster about the COESO Funding Landscape Study results at the [ECSA conference 2022](#) on October 5, 2022 (Berlin) (estimated 400 participants).

Subsequently, COESO wrote the [Funding Advocacy Action Plan](#) (COESO D.4.3) in October 2021, with relevant tips for funding entities as well as citizen science practitioners. The overall concept of COESO's funding advocacy activities was promoted through a blogpost ([“Funders and fundees: two sides of the same coin”](#)), and the advocacy action tips were promoted through a social media campaign on Twitter , always linking to the Zenodo document, which has been viewed 916 times and downloaded 324 times as of December 11, 2023.

Meanwhile, COESO engaged funders across Europe with workshops to discuss funding policies and practices that support participatory research in the social sciences and humanities. Funders were recruited to participate in 4 national workshops (Germany, Italy, Spain, France) through the various COESO WP4 consortium members networks. After the national funder workshops were complete, in the summer of 2022, the results were used to write [COESO's funding policy brief, “Foster funding for citizen science in the social sciences and humanities”](#) published June 30, 2022 [916 views; 324 downloads – Dec 11, 2023]. To promote the policy brief and the final international funder workshop, a “Reasons to FundCitSci” social media campaign was made, using video footage created by the COESO consortium and pilots members. The videos (3 in total) showed individual members showing and then passing a paper that says “SSH Citizen Science#FundCitSci”. The videos were directly embedded within the social media posts. They are also embedded on the [COESO website media page](#). Direct links are here: [Part 1](#), [Part 2](#), [Part 3](#).

In preparation for a final International Funder Workshop, the following blog posts, including those related to the national workshops, were published and promoted through social media:

- November 11, 2022: [“Funding citizen science: input from the Spanish funder community”](#)
- November 11, 2022: [“Funding citizen science: input from the Italian funder community”](#)
- December 13, 2022: [“Funding citizen science: input from the German funder community”](#)
- December 16, 2022: [“Announcing a workshop for funders: ‘Solving societal challenges with citizen science - the power of funding’”](#)
- January 1, 2023: [“Jan 25th: A workshop for funders”](#)
- January 9, 2023: [“Funding citizen science: input from the French funder community”](#)

Finally, in January 2023, COESO organized an international funder workshop. In total, the national and international workshop engaged representatives from 35 different funding entities across

Europe. After the international funder workshop, a semi-private (open link, but not published) living document, with links to all the COESO funding-related outputs, was created for and distributed to (and, as of December 2023, continues to be utilized) by funder representatives who attended. The purpose of the document is to facilitate the exchange of contact information for exploring specific funding practices with each other. Presentations made by four funders at the international workshop were recorded and are available to view on the COESO website. Direct links are here: [Michael Arentoft](#), DG R&I, European Commission; [Chiara Cardelli](#), LGB Open Innovation in Science; [Chris Manion](#), British Science Association, [Denise de Roux](#), WeMakelt. A blog post, [“Recap: International funder workshop”](#) (February 24, 2023), highlighting the international workshop and the policy brief was promoted through social media in February 2023.

In addition to engaging with funders, COESO also engaged with citizen science practitioners in January 2023 through a webinar in coordination with ECSA (European Citizen Science Association). Entitled, [“COESO Community Chat - getting money and momentum for social science and humanities in citizen science”](#), the webinar (29 attendees) shared concrete ideas and actions for citizen science practitioners to their funding opportunities and the recording remains available. It has been viewed 83 times (as of December 11, 2023) and was promoted through a blog post, [“Jan 17th: A webinar for the citizen science community”](#) (December 12, 2023) [29 live attendees; viewed 83 times on YouTube as of Dec 13 2023] accompanied by social media.

Furthermore, a [page](#) on the COESO website is dedicated to disseminating COESO’s funding advocacy results. There, all COESO’s funding related reports are available, as well as the video recordings of individual funder speeches from the international funder conference. Although the landscape study, the writing of the advocacy action plan, the funder workshops, and the writing/publishing of the funding policy brief, almost all took place in the first two years of the project, weekly social media posts were posted throughout the third year (2023) of the project, which included links to the relevant documents.

Finally, in order to further engage the funding community, the COESO consortium agreed to organize a final conference in collaboration with [PRO-Ethics](#), a Horizon 2020 funded project that worked with research and innovation funding organizations across Europe to test new, ethical ways to involve citizens in decision making processes. In October 2023, at the resulting joint final conference, [Connect.Collaborate.Create](#), Alessia Smaniotto (EHESS/Open Edition) presented COESO’s funding advocacy results, as part of the overall COESO results. Additionally, printed copies of COESO’s funding policy brief were distributed at one key conference workshop, designed and facilitated by a group of funders - workshop 2.2: “Shaping participatory futures: what can funders do to facilitate meaningful participation in and with science & innovation?” Additionally, three follow-up blog posts, written by conference presenters, highlight funding issues discussed at the conference: [“Promoting citizen science and fostering ethical participatory approaches to research funding”](#) by Marina Angelaki (published Nov 24, 2023), [“Reflections on the ‘Connect. Collaborate. Create.’ Conference from Science Europe by James Morris and Claire Salinas”](#) (published Nov 24, 2023) and [“Shaping participatory futures: what can funders do to facilitate meaningful participation in and with science & innovation?”](#) by Frederike Schmitz (published Dec 14, 2023).

5. Cooperation Analytics

Achievements:

As a “proof of concept” experimentation, Cooperation Analytics (CA) was communicated throughout the project through a total of 7 blog posts on the COESO website and intense participation and exchanges at international conferences and meetings with academic colleagues who are specifically interested in the topic of “cooperation”. Despite the narrow target audience, the two reports containing highly specialized technicalities have been cumulatively **viewed 380 times and downloaded 263 times**.

COESO’s work package 5 developed the “Cooperation Analytics” (CA), starting from the beginning of the project in January 2021. The CA progress was documented throughout the project through reports (3 in total) and blog posts (7 in total). Critically, because the tasks in this work package were research oriented, the WP5 team shared their methodologies and findings at a variety of conferences and meetings (10 in total) – thus constantly reflecting on their work, sharing their progress with colleagues, receiving feedback and exchanging ideas for how to define and measure “cooperation” in participatory research.

The first deliverable for WP5, [Cooperation analytics: criteria grid and development](#) (COESO D.5.1) was published in September 2021, and the progress that had been made thus far was shared by Jessica Pidoux (SciencesPo) Alessia Smaniotto (EHESS/Open Edition) at the [1st Global Transdisciplinarity Conference](#) (track on participatory evaluation; estimated 30 attendees). These actions were followed by four blog posts on the COESO website to explain how and why the criteria for analyzing cooperation were being developed: [Cooperation analytics for citizen science... what's that?](#) (published November 2021), [When science and society interact: a short history of conventions](#) (December 12, 2021), [COESO's Work Package 5 and the people behind](#) (January 7, 2022) and [What is Cooperation Analytics made of?](#) (January 21, 2022). The blog posts were used to feature the deliverable’s contents in a friendly and personable format and social media posts were used to promote the blog posts and the deliverable. In January 2022, Dominique Boullier (WP5, Sciences Po) presented to 20 directors of scientific information platforms (in French, they are known as “URFIST”s) where he discussed with the community about the connection between the infrastructure of Open Science and the field of Citizen Science at a European level, leveraging the literature review that had already been completed for Cooperation Analytics and its conceptual model. In March 2022, at the [Workshop Governance By Infrastructure`University of Lausanne](#), Jessica Pidoux introduced the COESO project, the plurality of definitions of Citizen Science, the contribution of the concept of cooperation, and expanding the theoretical framework to the case of data collectives in other case studies.

As the development of CA progressed, Jessica Pidoux (Sciences Po) and Dominique Boullier (Sciences Po) continued to participate in discussions, including in June 2022 at an online workshop called [Sustaining Knowledge and its Infrastructure: Digital knowledge infrastructures at the crossroads of governance practices](#), where they drew upon their work and results outlined in the [Report on Test and Final Development of the Cooperation Analytics](#) (COESO D.5.2), published June 2022, to add to the discussions with 15 colleagues on how “as socio-technical systems, digital knowledge infrastructures are essentially heterogeneous and unstable objects.” Further work on CA was shared through a presentations made in September 2022 by Jessica Pidoux (Sciences Po) and Dominique Boullier (Sciences Po) at the [ESPAnet conference in Vienna](#) (tract 7: Citizen Social Science and Social Innovation: New Practices for the Local Evidence-Based Social Policies), (estimated 200 attendees). And in November 2022 at the [Colloquium ethical issues of science and participatory research](#) at the university of Bordeaux

Dominique Boullier (Sciences Po) made a presentation titled “Ethical issues of participatory science and research in the field of political and social sciences – A calculable ethics? The cooperation indicators of the COESO project” (15 participants). To ensure this information about Cooperation Analytics reached a wider audience, a blog post was published in February 2023, [Why measuring citizen science is ethical: cooperation analytics is ethical](#), presenting in written form, what Dominique Boullier presented in oral form in Bordeaux. Dominique Boullier also presented Cooperation Analytics in January 2023 at Sorbonne Musée de l’homme Master Sciences Participatives.

In the final year of the COESO project, final preparations were made to test the Cooperation Analytics 23 indicators on data from five of the COESO pilots. Jessica Pidoux (Sciences Po) and Dominique Boullier (Sciences Po) continued to share about the development of Cooperation Analytics, including in January 2023 at a conference, [Two contemporary challenges for digital humanities](#) (Dominique) and in April 2023 at a workshop at the ColLab University of Lausanne through a presentation entitled [“Mesurer les pratiques de la science citoyenne: L’analyse de la coopération \(project COESO-H2020\)”](#), where Cooperation Analytics, including the context of COESO and VERA, were presented to approximately 20 participants and a further epistemological discussion about citizen science took place. In June 2023 Jessica Pidoux (Sciences Po) also participated in the [STS Oslo conference](#) (estimated 200 participants), where she introduced the COESO project and the notion of cooperation in citizen science as developed by WP5 in problems of infrastructures (and she also distributed VERA postcards). Two final blogposts, [Cooperation is trust, contracts, plurality](#) (June 28, 2023) and [23 indicators measuring the cooperation of COESO’s pilots](#) (July 31, 2023), on the COESO website help communicate about how the Cooperation Analytics indicators measure cooperation practices and how the results can be used. As usual, these blogposts were promoted with social media posts. Finally, at COESO’s final conference, [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#), Dominique Boullier (Sciences Po) and Jessica Pidoux (Sciences Po) collaboratively facilitated a specific session “Session 1.1D – Participatory evaluation and self-assessment applied to citizen science”, together with two other researchers to share the Cooperation Analytics results, as well as other perspectives on evaluation and assessment as it pertains to citizen science. The WP5 final [Report on activism and science within citizen science](#) (COESO D.5.3), will be published at the end of December, and social media posts to promote it will be scheduled for January 2024. The outcome of the data analysis, and the code and tools associated with the processing of this data will be managed via git (revision management system) and stored in Preste private github repositories (<https://github.com/PresteFront>).

6. Mutual Learning

Achievements:

COESO’s Mutual Learning Exercises (MLEs) with pilots and with journalists/researchers conducted throughout the project are useful as a prototype for developing future MLE programs in a variety of contexts. The MLEs are summarized in a blog post on the COESO website and within [Public Engagement, Mutual Learning, and Multimodal Practices in Citizen Science: report on the activities of WP6](#) (D.6.1) and further presented and discussed through a dedicated workshop at the COESO final conference and communicated through social media. The report has had **77 views** and **36 downloads** (as of Dec 11, 2023).

Mutual Learning Exercises (MLEs) were an integral aspect of the COESO project, as they contributed to the project’s objectives of supporting collaborative practices (objective 1), engaging with stakeholders from different backgrounds (objective 4), identifying obstacles and assessing

efficient collaborations (objective 5), and experimenting with new methodologies (objective 6). Although they were designed specifically for the needs within the framework of the COESO project, the methodologies used can be considered a prototype that other projects and groups can draw from as they develop their own mutual learning exercises. Nine blog posts on the COESO website are dedicated to communicating about the number of the online and in-person (in Marseille) MLE activities that took place among the pilot projects:

- [COESO's 1st Mutual Learning Exercise](#) (March 11, 2022)
- [COESO's 1st Mutual Learning Exercise, part II](#) (April 14, 2022)
- [A Collaborative Journey: the 2nd COESO's Mutual Learning Exercise in Marseille](#) (June 29, 2023)
- [Exploring Participatory Research with COESO pilot projects](#) (April 28, 2023)
- [A Collaborative Journey: the 2nd COESO's Mutual Learning Exercise in Marseille](#) (June 29, 2023)
- [Public Engagement, Mutual Learning, and Multimodal Practices in Citizen Science](#)

COESO also organized and facilitated a separate 2-day, in-person MLE in Paris that narrowed in on researchers and journalists who focus on issues related to organized crime, confiscated assets, policy and justice. They reflected together on their ongoing projects and working methods and discussed how reporters can work with researchers in a “solutions journalism” approach. The following blog posts were published to disseminate the results:

- [La Babel Academy, des journalistes et chercheur·euses enquêtent sur l'usage social des biens confisqués](#) (October 20, 2022)
- [Retours sur la Babel Academy. Journalistes et chercheur·euses autour de l'usage social des biens confisqués.](#) (May 25, 2023)
- [A look back at the Babel Academy. Journalists and researchers discussed the social reuse of confiscated assets.](#) (June 1, 2023)

Additionally, pilot #2 conducted several Mutual Learning Exercises within their project, as well as after the project officially ended, which they blogged about and reported on in [The movement of an embodied thought: Pilot 2 Dancing Philosophy Report](#) (COESO D.2.6). All COESO's MLE activities are summarized in the related public deliverable, [Public Engagement, Mutual Learning, and Multimodal Practices in Citizen Science: report on the activities of WP6](#) (COESO D.6.1.), published September 2023.

In October 2023, everyone involved in all the MLEs was invited to convene again at [Connect.Collaborate.Create](#). (COESO's final conference), where Alessia Smaniotto specifically presented COESO's MLEs within the session, *2.1K: Learning participatory research: creating common spaces for training and mutual learning*.

7. Communication about SSH Citizen Science

Achievements:

The online magazine Cafebabel, published a five-article series called “Common Grounds” (in three languages) based on COESO's pilot projects to provide information and context about how participatory research in the social sciences and humanities is carried out. In total, the articles received **2,040 clicks**. Similarly, Bulle Media produced a nine-episode podcast, “Exploring Citizen Science”; cumulatively, the episodes have been **downloaded 1,798 times** across all five continents.

COESO's fourth objective, "engage with stakeholders from different backgrounds" was accomplished, in part, through the dissemination of information through two mainstream media channels, a Podcast series: "Exploring Citizen Science" (COESO D.7.3) and an Article series: "Common Grounds" (COESO D.7.4). These media outlets tell stories about citizen science in the social sciences and humanities, especially about the work accomplished through the COESO pilots, in an engaging fashion for the general public. Over the project's lifetime, five articles were written and published on the online magazine, [Cafebabel](#), and nine podcast episodes were recorded and published by [BulleMedia](#).

The "Common Grounds" articles were promoted through social media, individually as they came out, and the series as a whole was promoted through a blogpost, [Cafébabel Terrains Communs: "Bridging the Gap: A Deep Dive into Collaborative Narratives"](#) (December 12, 2023) and social media posts scheduled through January 2024. Each "Common Grounds" article, upon publication, was made permanently available on the Cafebabel website and links to them were included in Cafebabel's newsletter, which has a database of 18,864 emails, in May 2023, October 2023, and November 2023. Additionally, COESO posted multiple tweets about each article on the project's Twitter/X. As of November 23, 2023, the links to the articles from the newsletter have received the following number of clicks:

- Article 1 French: 420
- Article 1 English: 193
- Article 1 Italian: 88
- Article 2 French: 352
- Article 2 English: 256
- Article 2 Italian: 94
- Article 3 French: 252
- Article 3 English: 145
- Article 3 Italian: 60
- Article 4 French: 125
- Article 4 English: 130
- Article 4 Italian: 25
- note: article 5 was published in December and the number of total clicks is not available at the time of writing this report

Information on the "[Exploring Citizen Science" podcast](#)" is available on the COESO website through a blogpost, "[A new year. A new podcast](#)" (January 2023) and on the dedicated [COESO media page](#). As the podcast specifically covers the COESO pilot projects, the pilot members were encouraged to spread information about the podcast through their various networks channels, and all COESO consortium members were encouraged to add the podcast link to their email signatures. The podcast was promoted through newsletter contributions, dedicated social media posts on the COESO X/Twitter account, as well as at various in-person events – through specific points within verbal presentations and the physical distribution of printed "seed cards" and stickers, at:

- ECSA conference Berlin, Germany (September 2022)
- Open Science Festival in Rotterdam, The Netherlands (August 2023)
- COESO Mutual Learning Exercises 2023, Marseille, France (June 2023)
- Open Science Fair, Madrid, Spain (September 2023)
- Connect.Collaborate.Create final conference, Paris, France (October 2023)

- Falling Walls, Berlin, Germany (November 2023)
- Munin Conference, Tromsø, Norway (November 2023)
- Journée nationale d'étude du réseau URFIST, Bordeaux, France (November 2023)

[Image of podcast sticker (size: A7)]

As of December 13, 2023, the podcast episodes have been downloaded, cumulatively, a total of 1,798 times and distributed geographically as depicted in the following map:

Downloads by location

Sep 28, 2022 – Dec 12, 2023 · All episodes

The podcast and the online magazine not only targeted the “general audience,” but the informal feedback we received indicated that they were also interesting for academic researchers. This target audience was also engaged through the various meetings mentioned in the section dissemination management, both through contributions in the meetings themselves and through joint actions we supported, such as collecting input to develop criteria to define what a citizen science project is, as described in [We need your input! Open consultation on citizen science criteria](#). Additionally, a number of scientific publications related to the project results (listed part

l of this document) were published in academic journals; they are also listed in the resources page of the COESO website. One key report targeted for the academic audience, [Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science](#) (COESO D.7.6) elaborates specifically on the specialized participatory research practices within social sciences and humanities disciplines that may help broaden the scope of how citizen science engages with society. The report will be promoted through pre-scheduled social media posts and newsletter contributions in 2024, after the COESO project has ended.

III. Assessment of Dissemination Measures

This section reviews the COESO project Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are relevant for the dissemination activities and their achievement.

1. Key Performance Indicators

The tables below show the relevant KPIs for the discussion on dissemination achievements. Seven indicators pertain specifically to communication work: 1) website audience, 2) social media audience, 3) number of final conference attendees, 4) number of workshop attendees, 5) newsletter audience, and 6) number of researchers on VERA, and number of citizen scientists on VERA. Another six pertain to the overall project: 1) Number of project enrolled in VERA, 2) number of new profiles on FundIt, 3) number of funding programs with “citizen science” as a criterion 4) Cumulated audience (no. of views) for transmedia products by the end of the project 5) Cumulated audience (no. of unique visitors) per pilot blog per month. For 11 of the 12 KPIs, COESO exceeded or came very close to meeting the target number. The remaining KPI requires a short assessment and explanation, and one other KPI (which was met) calls for a short explanation of how the number was derived.

Pilot’s blogs on Hypotheses.org impact measured by the “Cumulated audience (no. of unique visitors) per pilot blog per month” (target 150/month; achieved 40/month): In June 2022, the analytics generator for the Hypotheses blogs changed providers. After this change, we saw a distinct decrease in numbers in some of the blogs, and therefore we must be careful when analyzing the statistics. However, the discrepancy in numbers pre and post June 2022 may not account for the overall low number. Even with a dedicated community manager, it was a challenge to convince all the pilot members, who were very busy conducting their research in the short amount of time allotted, to be active bloggers. Pilots 2 and 3 were the most active bloggers, and their blogs received the most number of visits. While their projects were active, Pilot #2 averaged 133 visitors and pilot #3 averaged 153 visitors. This indicates that the target of 150/month is reasonable, but the pilot members need to have intrinsic motivation/interest and/or personnel support to post regular and engaging content.

Citizen science adoption by funders measured by “No. of funding programs adding citizen science as a criterion in FundIt” (target 5/ achieved 94): As part of the COESO WP4, FundIt added a “citizen sciences” tag option to the platform. Staff at FundIt then went through the existing FundIt funding programs database and added the new tag wherever relevant. They also did desk research to find additional citizen science funding calls to manually add to the database. In total, 185 funding calls published on the FundIt platform now have the “citizen sciences” tag. 94 of

those calls are specific citizen science calls, and most of those 94 calls would not have been published if the “citizen sciences” tag had not been added. In total, 22 new funders were added to the list of over 1,850 funding institutions represented on FundIt.

Additionally, it should be noted that our social media audience is not solely based on COESO-specific channels. Our only exclusively-“COESO” social media channel was on X/Twitter (803 followers on Dec 16 2023). X/Twitter underwent significant changes (ownership and algorithms) in the last year of the project, resulting in a large number of people in the community leaving the platform entirely. COESO also reached the community through the OPERAS social media channels (X/Twitter–3,255 followers, Instagram–76 followers, LinkedIn–950 followers, Facebook–236 follower; follower numbers obtained Dec 16 2023).

a. Communication KPIs

Action	KPI	Detail	Target (original)	New Target	Achieved (as of Dec 12 2023)
Project website	Audience	No. of visits/month	5,000	avg 1,000	avg 951 👍
Social media	Audience	No. of followers	1,500	1,500	3,255 👍
Final conference	Audience	No. of attendees	80	80	170 👍
Workshops	Audience	No. of attendees	30	300	314 👍
Newsletter*	Audience	No. of subscribers	200	500	651 👍
Outreach	Engagement	No. of researchers in VERA	50	50	49 👍
Outreach	Engagement	No. of citizen scientists in VERA	70	70	125 👍

*COESO does not have its own newsletter but was integrated into a joint newsletter ([The Citizen Engagement Quarterly](#)) as described in section 1, and COESO has a dedicated section in the OPERAS newsletter. The number listed here is calculated by adding the number of subscribers to *The Citizen Engagement Quarterly* and the number of subscribers to the OPERAS newsletter.

b. Relevant Project KPIs

KPI	Measurement	Original Target	New Target	Achieved (as of Dec 12 2023)
VERA uptake	No. of projects using/enrolled in the VERA platform	10	10	82 (15 public) 👍
Fundit Uptake	No. of new profiles (funders and other funding seekers) created on Fundit	30	30	280 👍
Citizen science adoption by funders	No. of funding programs adding citizen science as a criterion in FundIt	5	5	94 👍 😊

Transmedia products impact*	Cumulated audience (no. of views) by the end of the project	10,000	10,000	64,810 👍
Pilot's blogs on Hypotheses.org impact	Cumulated audience (no. of unique visitors) per blog per month	500/mo	150/mo	40 😊

*In this case, “transmedia” refers to the communication of the COESO project across a variety of media formats. For this KPI, the total number of views, over the project lifetime, was counted for: total COESO website visitors (33,294), total pilot blogs visitors (8,343), clicks on the Cafebabel articles (2,040), and podcast downloads (1,798), overall X/Twitter post engagements (13,000), overall number of COESO publication views on Zenodo (6,335)

IV. Conclusion

As mentioned earlier in this document, successful dissemination of scientific project results is not only a matter of making them findable and accessible. It also involves engaging with the communities who could and would use the results, if they knew about them. The results need to be presented in a meaningful, attractive, and appropriate manner for the specific audiences. To accomplish this in the COESO project, the practice of academic blogging was especially emphasized, both at the pilot level and at the project level. The pilot blogs independently, cumulatively, feature 119 posts. Additionally, 91 blog posts are published on the COESO website. These include entries about the pilots as well as other specific topics covered within the COESO project. Although this communication strategy supported result dissemination for researchers who had an interest in it and time to do it, other researchers may have preferred to explore other formats. For many, though, the main factor preventing them from putting more effort into their blogs was the time it took to write them. Exploring how to make blogging or other communication actions less time consuming, or investigating how much extra time is really needed for these types of “alternative” or additional dissemination formats, might be helpful for convincing funders, or the overall research assessment system, to reconsider the time constrictions placed on researchers. To support good communication practices, extra time and financial support is needed.

In addition to blogging, COESO also integrated the practices of podcasting and working with journalists to disseminate research results. The COESO podcast episodes were downloaded a significant number of times, indicating that there is more potential to be explored in this area – future projects could consider taking advantage of the existence of the “Exploring Citizen Science” series, or starting their own. The practice of involving journalists within a research project to explore alternative media formats to communicate research can also be integrated into future projects, and COESO’s work serves as an example for expanding a project’s audience.

Through an engaged and passionate consortium and group of pilot members, combined with an ambitious communication and dissemination plan, the COESO project has successfully communicated and disseminated each of its project outputs to its target audiences. Most critically, COESO has successfully jump-started the VERA community. The citizen science community is already engaging with the VERA website, which will continue – under the coordination of the [OPERAS](#) infrastructure – to support citizen science and participatory research in the social sciences and humanities beyond the COESO project lifetime. COESO’s successful final conference is a testament to the desire and willingness of the targeted audiences to be

interested in the project's results – 170 participants (218 registered) – mainly from Europe, but also from participants traveling from Africa, the United States, and Latin America – engaged in conversation about the specifics of conducting and supporting citizen science and participatory research. COESO's numerous reports will help inform the social sciences and humanities community on how to further uptake citizen science; the VERA hub gives them a place to convene, organize themselves into projects, and find funding; the project's mutual learning exercises were the beginning of many important conversations, and they left behind a framework for important knowledge exchange to continue; the experimentation with building Cooperation Analytics proved that it is possible and useful to measure collaboration, and the concept is ready to be expanded upon; and the online magazine articles and podcast episodes give body and form to abstract concepts, for the general public as well as the academic community, to further engage. And all of this practical information is available with just a couple mouse clicks, in open access format, from the COESO website, ready to feed and inspire the next projects to come.

The communication and dissemination within the COESO project explored ways to best reach the audience of the SSH citizen science community. It also aimed to enhance the visibility of citizen science project results in the SSH, contributing to fostering and strengthening the development of citizen science and participatory research in the social sciences and humanities.

Annexes

Annex 1: Dissemination Summary Table

Table 1. Summary of dissemination actions for each COESO project output

result (p#)=pilot# note: result names are abbreviated versions	Social media posts	New s letter posts	Conf erence Presenta tions	Post card /sticker	Post er	Print ed versio n	Zeno do	COE SO web site	Blog post
D..1.2 DMP							✓	✓	
D.1.4 Funding policy brief	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓	
D.2.1 Open Call Guide	✓	✓					✓	✓	
D.2.2. Pilot Blogs (p1-10)	✓		✓	✓10	✓13		✓	✓	
D.2.4 MemoRekall (p2)	✓		✓				✓	✓	✓
D.2.5 Choreographic Score (p2)	✓		✓				✓	✓	✓
D.2.6 Dancing Philosophy report (p2)	✓						✓	✓	✓
D.2.7 Solutions Journalism output (p3)	✓						✓	✓	✓
D.2.8 sensitive databases (p4)	✓						✓	✓	✓
D 2.9 sharing confidential data (p4)	✓						✓	✓	✓
D2.10 writing across borders (p5)	✓						✓	✓	✓
VERA website	✓	✓	✓	✓	1		✓	✓	✓
D.3.1 VERA user experience design							✓	✓	✓
D.3.2 VERA core design							✓	✓	
D3.3 VERA dashboard							✓	✓	
D.3.4 VERA matching interface							✓	✓	
D.3.5 VERA tools and services	✓						✓	✓	✓
D.3.6 VERA widget	✓						✓	✓	✓
D.4.1 Funding landscape study	✓	✓	✓		1		✓	✓	✓
D.4.2 VERA funding tool	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
D.4.3 Funding advocacy action plan	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	

D.5.1 CA criteria grid	✓		✓				✓	✓	✓
D.5.2 CA test and final development	✓		✓				✓	✓	
D.5.3 Report on activism within CS							✓	✓	
D.6.1 WP6 activities	✓		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓
D.6.2 Multimodal website	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	
D.7.1 Comms and Dissemination strategy							✓	✓	
D.7.2 Dissemination material guide							✓	✓	
D.7.3 Podcast series	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	
D.7.4 Article series	✓						✓	✓	
D.7.5 COESO dissemination							✓	✓	
D.7.6 SSH contribution to CS							✓	✓	
AGORAge Caring Community Toolkit	✓	✓	✓				✓	✓	✓

Annex 2: COESO pilot communication activities and outputs

Table 2: Selection* of communication activities and outputs by COESO pilots

<p>Pilot #1: Mass tourism’s impact on urban communities</p> <p>COESO Blog: https://civtur.hypotheses.org/ [21 blog posts]</p> <p>Related websites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://cria.org.pt/en/projects/coeso-collaborative-engagement-on-societal-issues • https://saojose.huma-num.fr/intro <p>Social Media: #TourismObservatory</p> <p>Poster: “How does mass tourism change the Lisbon’s António district?”</p> <p>Publications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VIDAL, Frédéric, Elisa Lopes da SILVA, Camilo LEÓN-QUIJANO, “Dwelling and everyday life in Lisbon: tourism and other urban practices” V Midterm Conference of European Sociological Association’s Research Network 37 (Urban Sociology), Berlin, November 2022 • SILVA Elisa Lopes da, Frédéric VIDAL, Susana FONSECA “From Lisbon to the Planet: environmental scales in tourism shaping the city”, ECSA CONFERENCE 2022, Berlin, November 2022 • Lisbon Tourism Observatory Final Report (COESO D.2.3) published Jan 2023 • Featured in Cafebabel Magazine article: “Citizen science and sensitive subjects: the case of the mass tourism”, November 15, 2023 • Featured in “Exploring Citizen Science” podcast in two episodes: “In Lisbon - part 1: Easier said than done” and “In Lisbon - part 2: Citizen Science hands-on”, April 20, 2023 • São José website : une analyse collective de l’expérience touristique à Lisbonne (projet COESO), February 27, 2023 <p>Presentations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • November 2021: “Encontro Nacional de Ciência Cidadã 2021: Construir pontes para uma ciência participada”: SILVA, Elisa Lopes da, Frédéric VIDAL, Israel GUARDA e Susana FONSECA and “Cidade (In)visível. Turismo e outras práticas quotidianas em Lisboa”, Biblioteca Municipal de Oeiras • June 2022: ECSA conference (Berlin) • October 2022: Connect.Collaborate.Create. (Paris)
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<p>Pilot #2: Dancing Philosophy: desire through dance and philosophy COESO Blog: https://dansophie.hypotheses.org/ [23 blog posts] Related websites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.cadmiumcompagnie.com/ • https://www.beseated.art/ • https://memorekall.com/fr/prototype-memorekall-iiif/ <p>Social Media: #DancingPhilosophy; https://twitter.com/LupettiLupino Poster: How do we think with our body? Publications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MemoRekall capsule: “Les mots” • MemoRekall capsule: “Désir” • MemoRekall capsule: “Une personne. Prendre, déposer, s'asseoir, se lever” • l'exemple avec le pilot 2: https://coeso.tetras-libre.fr/ • le bac à sable: https://iiif.tetras-libre.fr/ • le code du proto: https://gitlab.tetras-libre.fr/iiif/POC-mirador • Documenting collaborations with video annotation: MemoRekall Capsules (COESO D.2.4) [pilot 2], published May 2022 • Dancing Philosophy – Choreographic Score (COESO D.2.5), published June 2022 • The movement of an embodied thought: Pilot 2 Dancing Philosophy Report (COESO D.2.6) [pilot 2], published June 2022 <p>Presentations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • June 2021: RESAW Conference “Mainstream vs marginal content in Web history and Web archives”, Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History (C²DH) / Université du Luxembourg (Luxembourg) • May 2022: Table ronde.Les Rencontres TMNlab #23 : Médiation numérique du spectacle vivant, hybridité et enjeux politiques, Université rennes 2 (Rennes) • September 2022: Séminaire international Digital humanities in theatre studies: the researcher and the digital archive. Narratives from a user-oriented approach. Digital humanities in the performing arts. Methods in research and education, Performing Arts Hub Norway, European Network of Information Centres for Performing Arts (Oslo) • June 2022: Computational Methods for Theatre Studies? an online panel series May-July 2022, organized by Ulf Otto (LMU Munich) and Nora Probst (Univ. of Paderborn) • June 2022: Poster at 9th Living Knowledge Conference 2022 (Groningen, The Netherlands) • October 2022: Connect.Collaborate.Create. (Paris)
<p>Pilot #3: Social impacts of redistributing property confiscated from the mafia COESO Blog: https://usbc.hypotheses.org/ [12 blog posts] Related websites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://cafebabel.com/ • https://crimhalt.org/ <p>Social Media: #SocialReuseofConfiscatedAssets Poster: How does the Italian law on the social use of confiscated mafia assets enable citizen participation? Publications:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Three articles on Cafebabel Magazine (#changement de propriétaire) • Solutions journalism outputs (COESO D.2.7) [pilot 3], published June 2022 • Featured in Cafebabel Magazine article: “Citizen science and sensitive subjects: the case of the mass tourism” “The researcher-journalist duo, the recipe for a top notch investigation”, September 7, 2023 <p>Presentations::</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • March 15, 2022: Crim'HALT auditionnée par SciencesPo Alumni ESS & EI • December 29, 2022: Interview with eu!radio • October 2022: Connect.Collaborate.Create. (Paris)
<p>Pilot #4: Tools and databases to increase the impact of investigative journalism COESO Blog: https://thebackstory.hypotheses.org/ [7 blog posts] Related websites:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://crimotech.it/ • https://www.irpi.eu/ <p>Social Media: #SensitiveDataSharing Poster: Tools and databases to increase the impact of investigative journalism</p>

Publications:

- <https://irpimedia.irpi.eu/centocelle-criminalita-organizzata/>
- [Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases](#) (COESO D.2.8) [pilot 4], published April 2022
- [Report on the technical and legal framework for sharing confidential data](#) (COESO D.2.9) [pilot 4], published March 2022

Presentations:

- (various dates in 2022) [CSABOT training sessions](#)
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

Pilot #5: Growing migrant knowledge: contemporary and historical perspectives

COESO Blog: <https://migconn.hypotheses.org/> [9 blog posts]

Related websites:

- <https://www.migrantconnections.org/>
- <https://migrantknowledge.org/>

Social Media: #MigrantKnowledge

Poster: [Growing Migrant Knowledge: Contemporary and Historical Perspectives](#)

Publications:

- [“Introducing “Migrant Connections:” A Digital History Research Hub for Learning and Participatory Activity by/for/with Citizen Scholars,”](#) blog post for Public Humanities, September 13, 2021, (Jana Keck)
- Kinder lasen Briefe vor,” Interview for Spiegel Geschichte 2022/1 (Jana Keck and Simone Lässig)
- Featured in Cafebabel Magazine article: [“Uncovering the lives of first generation immigrants, letter by letter,”](#) April 24 , 2023
- [“Writing Across Borders” outputs](#) (COESO D.2.10) [pilot 5], published December 2022

Presentations:

- May 18, 2021: SLAM [Societies, Libraries, Archives, and Museums] Idea Showcase,” National Genealogical Society conference (virtual) (Atiba Pertilla)
- July 23, 2021: “Migrant Connections project presentation,” International German Genealogical Partnership conference (virtual) (Atiba Pertilla)
- October 19, 2021: “The Present and Future of Transcription,” Digital Cultural Heritage D.C. Meetup (virtual) (Atiba Pertilla)
- January 12, 2022: "From Family Research to Digital History," University of Bremen Public History program (virtual)
- March 23, 2022: "Launch of New Digital Research Infrastructure: 'Migrant Connections,'" GHI Washington (virtual) (Daniel Burckhardt, Jana Keck, Atiba Pertilla)
- June 2-4, 2022: Conference “Datafication in the Historical Humanities: Reconsidering Traditional Understandings of Sources and Data” at the GHI Washington (Washington D.C.) (Daniel Burckhardt, Jana Keck, Simone Lässig, Atiba Pertilla)
- July 19, 2022: Migrant Connections,” invited talk, International German Genealogical Partnership board (virtual)
- August 18, 2022: Researching Mobile Lives – Sources, Methods, and Opportunities in Digital Public History,” panel discussion at International Federation for Public History Conference 2022 (Berlin) (Jana Keck)
- November, 2022: Final Symposium of “Writing Across Borders,” (Bonn) (Daniel Burckhardt and Simone Lässig)
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)
- January 7, 2023: “Migrant Connections: A Digital Research Infrastructure for German-American History,” Poster Presentation at the American Historical Association Conference 2023, (Jana Keck)
- February 7, 2023: "'Migrant Connections' and the Potential of Transatlantic Digital Research," University of Texas-Austin Department of Germanic Studies, Austin, Texas, (Jana Keck and Atiba Pertilla)
- February 27, 2023: “News from Germany: “Migrant Connections” and the Potential of Transatlantic Digital Research,” George Mason University, (Jana Keck and Atiba Pertilla)
- March 15, 2023: “Opening Sources – modulare Wege zur Quellenbereitstellung und -edition,” panel discussion at Annual Conference of Digital Humanities in the German-Speaking Environment (DHd 2023), (Daniel Burckhardt and Jana Keck)
- March 16, 2023: "Introducing 'Migrant Connections,'" Digital Business History workshop, Business History Conference, Detroit, Michigan, (Atiba Pertilla)
- March 16, 2023: "Introducing 'Migrant Connections,'" Digital Business History workshop, Business History Conference, Detroit, Michigan, (Atiba Pertilla)

- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

Pilot #6: Digital mapping with disabled citizens in Germany (DiMDiCi)

COESO Blog: <https://dimdici.hypotheses.org/> [12 blog posts]

Related websites:

- <https://www.hs-gesundheit.de/departments/doch-department-of-community-health/uebersicht>
- <https://www.itc.nl/>
- <https://www.wittekindshof.de/herne>
- <https://www.herne.de/>

Social Media: #InclusiveMapping

Poster: [Digital Mapping with Disabled Citizens](#)

Publications:

- Ogito_Herne will be made available on GitHub
- International publication in preparation
- Featured in Cafebabel Magazine article: “[Empowering inclusive communities: citizen science unites for vulnerable populations in Europe](#)”, December 11, 2023

Presentations:

- November 23-24, 2022: [Community Health Conference](#) as part of ParStar project (Bochum)
- February, 15 2023: [The Urban Health Transdisciplinary Forum](#), as part of ParStar project
- March 20-23, 2023: [Armut und Gesundheit](#) (Berlin); publication highlighted in [Bundesgesundheitsblatt](#) and on [episode 46 of Armut und Gesundheit podcast](#)
- April 18-21, 2023: [Citizen Science Conference](#). “Forschungskiosk” (Linz)
- May 5, 2023: European Protest Day for the Equality of People with Disabilities (Herne) highlighted in [Teilhabe barrierefrei gestalten](#)
- May 23, 2023: final event HS Gesundheit (Bochum)
- June 28, 2023: Bochum Poster presentation on the Day of Research
- August 23, 2023: Herne “Fachbereich Soziales” Inclusion Advisory Board Meeting
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

Pilot #7: Ageing in a caring community (AGORAge)

COESO Blog: <https://agorage.hypotheses.org/> [12 blog posts]

Related websites:

- <https://www.marc.urv.cat/es/investigacion-transferencia/projectes-de-recerca/agorage-esp/>
- <https://www.israa.it/>

Social Media: @AGORAgeproject #AGORAge

Poster: [Ageing in a Caring Community](#)

Publications:

- Riccò I., De Stefani A. & Anleu Hernández C. (2022) [Notes de Recerca: AGORAge. Arxiu d’Etnografia de Catalunya](#) (24), pp.238-242.
- AGORAge Caring Community Toolkit - [English](#), [Italian](#), [French](#), [Catalan](#), [Spanish](#)
- Autumn 2023/Winter 2024 (abstract accepted) Riccò I., Anleu Hernández C. & De Stefani A. (2023-2024) Building together a caring community for the well-being of older people (provisional title), Social inclusion journal.
- Featured in Cafebabel Magazine article: “[Empowering inclusive communities: citizen science unites for vulnerable populations in Europe](#)”, December 11, 2023

Presentations:

- May 3-4 2023: Conference “EUSEA2023 Pathfinders on a Mission: Exploring Engagement in a Complex World” organized by Eusea, Bolzano (Italy), oral presentation by Isabella Riccò and Adele De Stefani EUSEA Conference #EUSEA2023 Bolzano, Italy Pathfinders on a Mission: Exploring Engagement in a Complex World!
- September 20, 2022 Conference “Identidades Comunes: Second National Meeting of Citizen Science – Social Science and Humanities”, organized by Ibercivis, (Zaragoza, Spain), oral presentation by Isabella Riccò. [Watch on YouTube.](#)
- 2022/2023: Qualitative research methodology and nursing, 2022/2023, nursing degree, Campus Catalunya-URV (84 Students)
- 2022/2023: Design and advanced techniques in Medical Anthropology III, Master in Medical Anthropology and Global Health-URV (20 students)
- January 25, 2023: Webinar “Solving Societal Challenges with Citizen Science – The Power of Funding” organized by COESO, oral presentation by Isabella Riccò and Adele de Stefani
- July 2023 Presentation of the final version of the Community Map, Borgo Mazzini Smart Cohousing

- July-September 2023 Presentation and distribution of the Booklet to the residents who participated in the AGORAge pathway, Casa Albergo
- 2022/2023: Qualitative research methodology and nursing, nursing degree, Baix Penèdes-URV (38 Students)
- September 5-8, 2023: 2023 Conference “[XVI Congreso Antropología 2023](#)”, organized by ASAAE, la Coruña (Spain), oral presentation by Isabella Riccò & Claudia Anleu
- November 23, 2023 Seminar “caring communities vs community care”, organized by ICA and ITA, URV, round table
- Autumn 2023: Social Anthropology Research Group Seminar: the main results of the project presented to researchers, professors, and students.
- August 31, 2022: Official presentation of the project to residents and professionals and delivery of the surveys, Casa Albergo.
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

Pilot #8: Women Water Watch

COESO Blog: <https://waterwatch.hypotheses.org/> [9 blog posts]

Related websites:

- <https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/projects/women-water-watch/>
- <https://afo.ortz/>

Social Media: #womenWATERwatch

Poster: [Mapping water quality from the river to the glass in Tanzania](#)

Publications:

- 2 student reports and 1 student dissertation forthcoming
- Spring 2023: Interview in the IOB alumni magazine “[Exchange to Change](#)” #51
- Mentioned in [IOB annual report 2022](#)
- Featured in Cafebabel Magazine article: “[Researchers are working with local communities to make a tangible impact](#)”, April 26, 2023
- Featured in “Exploring Citizen Science” podcast in episode: “[Lunch boxes, videogames and more](#)”, June 13, 2023

Presentations:

- January 25, 2023: Webinar “Solving Societal Challenges with Citizen Science – The Power of Funding” organized by COESO, oral presentation
- February 9, 2023: [Citizen Science in Tanzania ... the new magic bullet?](#)
- March 29, 2023: [International seminar at UHasselt on ‘Global partnerships- the route to sustainable and equitable partnerships’](#)
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

Pilot #9: Playful Futures

COESO Blog: <https://playfutures.hypotheses.org/> [3 blog posts]

Related websites:

- <https://edgeriders.eu/c/earthos/playful-futures/427>
- <https://www.tantlab.aau.dk/>
- <https://culturehubcroatia.hr/en/>

Social Media: #PlayfulFutures

Poster: [Playful futures. Raising awareness about climate change issues through gaming activities](#)

Publications:

- [A short report from Paris, Oct 21, 2023](#)
- Featured in “Exploring Citizen Science” podcast in episode: “[Lunch boxes, videogames and more](#)”, June 13, 2023

Presentations:

- August 3, 2023: Playful Futures Ethnographic results presentation (online)
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

Pilot #10: LUNCH-BOX-MONITOR

COESO Blog: <https://lunchbox.hypotheses.org/> [11 blog posts]

Related websites:

- <https://www.ugent.be/en>
- <https://www.letus.be/>
- <https://www.rikolto.org/>
- <https://www.gezondleven.be/>

Social Media: #LunchBoxMonitor

Poster: [Lunch Box Monitor: Insight into the nutritional quality of school lunch-boxes to assess food insecurity among primary school children in Belgium](#)

Publications:

- Featured in “Exploring Citizen Science” podcast in episode: “[Lunch boxes, video games and more](#)”, June 13, 2023

Presentations:

- June 14-17, 2023: [ISBNPA conference](#) (Uppsala, Sweden)
- October 2022: [Connect.Collaborate.Create.](#) (Paris)

*Throughout the project, the pilot project members informed COESO about their communication activities. Although an effort was made to record them all, this list may not include all activities.